

**EXPLORATORY STUDY ON POOR GOVERNANCE AND
PERSISTENCE OF HUMAN TRAFFICKING IN SOUTH WEST
NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The persistence and prevalence of human trafficking across African region has continued to pose worries among academics and other stakeholders in the continent. Despite the existing legislation against human trafficking in virtually all African countries, the menace persists, thereby impeding the realisation of sustainable development goals. Interestingly, several researches have been carried out on human trafficking in Nigeria, but few studies have explored how poor governance influences the persistence of human trafficking in south western Nigeria. Therefore, it would serve as the thrust of this study. The study seeks to answer the question: To what extent does poor governance influence the persistence of human trafficking in south western Nigeria?

Materials and Methods

An exploratory research design was used in the study. Qualitative approaches are suitable for researching the complex and multidimensional dynamics of human trafficking because they enable a full examination of the experiences, perceptions, and social conditions of those involved. Unlike quantitative approaches, which may oversimplify or overlook essential aspects of the phenomenon, qualitative research enables a more in-depth understanding of the

underlying elements that contribute to the persistence of human trafficking.

Results

The outcome of the study showed that majority of the victims of human trafficking were successfully recruited and transported by the traffickers due to manifestation of corruption-related activities at the border which is a pointer of poor governance. It is recommended that there should be efficient implementation of legislation that is devoid of corruption against human trafficking activities in Nigeria.

Keywords: Trafficking, poor governance, persistence, corruption, Nigeria

Introduction

Human trafficking is a serious and ongoing issue in many nations, including Nigeria. Economic, political, and cultural factors have combined to transform this region into a major hub for human trafficking. Despite significant local and international efforts to abolish this horrible crime, human trafficking continues, undermining human rights and creating cycles of poverty and brutality (Ukhami, Halidu, and Achudume 2024). According to Bigio and Vogelstein, 2021, the biggest contributor to this long-term issue is weak governance, which fails to address the underlying causes and exacerbates the problem in certain cases. To understand the role of poor governance in perpetuating human trafficking in South-west Nigeria, one must consider the larger sociopolitical environment, the specific factors that contribute to trafficking, and the demographic characteristics of the victims and offenders involved in this illegal activity.

Nigeria's governance has long been characterised by corruption, inefficiency, and a lack of accountability (Ogunlela, 2020). These difficulties have greatly weakened the state's ability to protect its citizens against human trafficking. Inadequate governance expresses itself in a variety of ways, including ineffective law enforcement, weak legal systems, and government involvement in trafficking. Due to the slim chances of detection or prosecution, these concerns foster an environment where traffickers can operate without fear of detection or punishment (Ogunlela, 2020). According to evidence, Nigerian law enforcement officers usually encounter limited financial resources,

inadequate training, and occasional cooperation with trafficking networks (Chikaodili, 2021). The lack of efficient law enforcement not only promotes trafficking but also discourages victims from seeking assistance because they believe the authorities are indifferent or incapable of protecting them.

Furthermore, despite their broad scope, Nigeria's legislative frameworks for combating human trafficking frequently fall short of effective implementation. The Trafficking in Persons (Prohibition) Enforcement and Administration Act of 2015 provides harsh penalties for trafficking crimes while also providing safeguards for victims. However, weak governance frequently impedes the full execution of these standards. Governments seldom hold traffickers accountable for their activities due to a lack of commitment to prioritising anti-trafficking operations and widespread corruption in the legal system. (Ukhami, Halidu, and Achudume 2024) Human trafficking continues due to inadequate law enforcement, which encourages the idea that there is no punishment for these crimes (chikaodili, 2021).

Another critical component of weak governance is the inability to address the socioeconomic situations that make people vulnerable to trafficking in the early stages. Widespread poverty, unemployment, and restricted access to education are important contributors to the prevalence of human trafficking in Nigeria, particularly in the South-west (Wuyah, and Mailamba 2019). Inadequate governance exacerbates these issues by failing to provide enough social services and economic opportunities, causing many people, particularly women and children, to be anxious for any opportunity to improve their situation, even if it means risking exploitation. Individuals' despair is used by traffickers, who deceive them with false promises of work possibilities, education, or a better life abroad, only to subject them to involuntary labour, sexual abuse, or various other forms of mistreatment (Oyindamola, Bidemi, and Atta, 2023).

The socioeconomic realities in South-west Nigeria intricately link to the factors that fuel human trafficking. Poverty is the primary reason, creating an ideal environment for traffickers to recruit victims. Traffickers usually target society's most vulnerable people, particularly those who have limited economic options, education, and social support networks. Women and children are frequently more vulnerable to

violence because they lack perceived authority in the socioeconomic structure (chikaodili, 2021). Aside from poverty, additional factors contributing to these issues include gender discrimination, limited educational opportunities, and societal and cultural traditions that perpetuate the exploitation of specific groups (Bako, M.J. and Syed, J., 2018).

Gender disparities are a common issue in Nigeria, and they have a significant impact on the dynamics of human trafficking. Females are commonly marginalised within society, particularly in the northern states, with limited possibilities for education and jobs. The act of marginalising these people makes them more vulnerable to traffickers who offer them better chances in other regions. These cultural behaviours, such as the practice of marrying young and undervaluing female children, exacerbate this vulnerability (Kempadoo, and Doezema, 2018). Families frequently surrender their girls to traffickers, either mistakenly or on purpose, in the misguided notion that doing so will secure a brighter future for them (Mills, 2023).

Despite substantial attempts by the Nigerian government and international groups to combat human trafficking, the practice remains deeply embedded in South-west Nigeria. Human traffickers continue to use this region as a major hub, bringing in a large number of victims, particularly women and children (Ukhami, Halidu, and Achudume 2024). The continued presence of human trafficking in south-west Nigeria raises serious concerns about the efficacy of current measures and the underlying factors that fuel this criminal activity. A major worry is the impact of ineffective governance, which not only fails to fight human trafficking but may also unwittingly allow it to continue (Bigio, and Vogelstein, 2021).

Poor governance worsens the socioeconomic drivers of human trafficking, such as poverty, unemployment, and gender inequality. The government's failure to provide basic social amenities, economic opportunities, and education creates vulnerabilities that traffickers exploit. Cultural practices and cultural customs compound the problem by legitimising the exploitation of vulnerable groups, such as women and children. The issue is broad and complex, requiring a detailed understanding of how insufficient governance contributes to the continuance of human trafficking. To effectively combat human

trafficking in South-west Nigeria, it is critical to address the underlying governance issues and socioeconomic elements that contribute to the problem. Failure to do so will produce unproductive results and leave a large number of people vulnerable to victimisation.

Literature Review

The concept of governance

Governance is the fulcrum essential for the development and progress of societies across the globe. It is vital to note that like most concepts in social and behavioural sciences, there are numerous definitions of governance. However, governance essentially refers to the complex processes, norms, and institutions that collectively oversee and regulate community functioning. In other words, governance represents the guiding principles that influence decisions, actions, and interactions which in turn establish the framework within which order and progress can flourish (Patterson et al., 2017). Governance is defined as the process or function of exercising authority, usually legitimate, to manage the affairs of people within a specific territory, often a state (Aiyede, 2023). Also, governance is how power is exercised in the management of a country's social and economic resources for development (Tarverdi, Saha & Campbell, 2019). Furthermore, governance encompasses activities driven by shared objectives, which may or may not stem from legal or formally designated duties and do not necessarily depend on authoritative power to ensure compliance. In a nutshell, governance is a broader concept that includes governmental institutions while also encompassing informal, non-governmental mechanisms through which individuals and organisations within its scope progress, meet their needs, and achieve their goals (Ekundayo, 2017).

By classifying political institutions according to their hierarchical structures, Aristotle is recognised as one of the first political thinkers to investigate the concept of governance. In order to shed light on various systems of government, he distinguished three primary types: democracy, autocracy, and dictatorship (Yang, 2021). Similarly, Kautilya, a well-known personality in India from around 2,300 years ago, demonstrated a remarkable similarity between his principles of state administration and the modern Welfare State model. Kautilya stressed the vital roles that rulers must play in defending the interests and well-

being of the state, community, and people even in prehistoric times (Choudhary, 2021). It is pertinent to note that his governance framework included inclusive programs aimed at uplifting marginalised and disadvantaged groups, showcasing his forward-thinking approach to social welfare and equity (Choudhary, 2021). This implies that the essence of governance is to meet the needs of her citizens and protect them as well.

The concept of Human Trafficking

The term trafficking was used to refer to the illicit trade in products, especially the gruesome trade in human beings (International Organization for Migration [IOM], 2018). In other words, trafficking is a system of exploitation, coercion, and oppression, in which human lives are undervalued and viewed as nothing more than commodities for profit. It is vital to note that the term human trafficking and trafficking in person are umbrella terms that are commonly utilised interchangeably when discussing criminal activity where individuals such as adults or children are exploited by traffickers for labour or sexual purposes (United States Department of State, 2023). This exploitative practice involves compelling victims to engage in various forms of activities against their will which allow traffickers to profit by exploiting the vulnerability and desperation of these individuals. consequently, victims of trafficking often endure severe physical, emotional, and psychological trauma, as they are coerced and manipulated into these situations of exploitation.

The International Labour Organization (ILO, 2006) defined trafficking in Nigeria as a form of child abuse and neglect, where children are moved from one location to another for exploitative labour. The International Organization for Migration (IOM, 2001) stated that trafficking involves the illegal engagement (through recruitment, kidnapping, or sale) and movement of migrants, whether within national borders or internationally, by intermediaries (traffickers) who profit through deception, coercion, and exploitation, violating the migrants' fundamental human rights. The most comprehensive definition, however, is found in the United Nations (UN) Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children (UN, 2000). Chief Mrs. Amina Titi Atiku Abubakar, wife of the former Vice President of Nigeria and then Chairperson of the Anti-

Trafficking NGO in Nigeria, signed the protocol on behalf of Nigeria. Article 3 of the protocol defines trafficking as the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring, or receipt of persons by means of threat, force, coercion, abduction, fraud, deception, abuse of power, or vulnerability, or through the giving or receiving of payments to obtain consent for exploitation. Exploitation includes, at a minimum, sexual exploitation, forced labour or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude, or the removal of organs. The consent of the victim is irrelevant if any of the aforementioned means have been employed. Even if none of these means are used, the act of recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring, or receipt for the purpose of exploitation is still considered “trafficking in persons.” A child is defined as any person under 18 years of age. This definition emphasises that trafficking is characterised by the exploitation of a child or adult being relocated.

Furthermore, Jatau (2019) identified three key components of human trafficking: the act, the means, and the purpose. The act refers to the recruitment or harbouring of victims, the means involve fraud and force, and the purpose is exploitation. Victims of human trafficking therefore, often face challenges such as poverty, low levels of education, youth, unemployment, sexual abuse, lack of family support, and living in vulnerable environments. Thus, human trafficking encompasses both smuggling and exploitation. Okereke and Okoli (2020) on the other hand, explain that human trafficking can be classified as internal when it occurs within a country, or external (cross-border) when it involves movement across national borders. Internal human trafficking is often for purposes such as illegal adoption and domestic servitude, while external trafficking typically involves commercial sexual exploitation, labour exploitation, and organ harvesting. In cases of cross-border trafficking, countries such as Nigeria, Togo among others are primary sources from which child labourers are transported through nations such as Equatorial Guinea, Niger and other West African countries to Europe for exploitation. However, the current study focused on human trafficking in South-West Nigeria.

Drivers of Human Trafficking in South-West Nigeria

Farr (2005) explains that push and pull factors are often cited as the primary drivers of human trafficking. “Push” factors, such as poverty,

gender inequality, and limited economic opportunities in source states, compel individuals to migrate and fuel the human labour trade. Conversely, pull factors in destination areas include the promise of a better quality of life, job opportunities, and the demand for cheap labour. The World Bank (2018) reported that over 45 percent of Nigeria's population lives in poverty, and this situation has worsened since the beginning of the 21st century. As a result, many families are at increased risk of being trafficked into prostitution or forced labour. Rotimi (2001) argued that a significant number of adolescents, especially those from polygamous families, often leave their homes in villages and slums where resources have become scarce in search of a better life, making them particularly vulnerable to traffickers.

Olubukola's (2020) study highlights the significant impact that Nigeria's poor leadership and corruption have had on the country's high unemployment rate and its involvement in human trafficking. World Bank data from 2021 (World Bank, 2022) indicates that more than 2.5 million people in Nigeria live in states plagued by violence due to militant disturbances, which often exacerbate issues such as human trafficking, migration, and poverty. Additionally, the common practice of sending children to live with wealthier relatives or friends may contribute to human trafficking in Nigeria (Nnamuchi et al., 2022). This cultural tradition, often involving financial transactions, is intended to provide young people with better opportunities to escape poverty and improve their lives. However, these practices can be exploited by human traffickers who profit significantly from them (Nnamuchi et al., 2022).

Furthermore, Ojomo (2005) identified several root causes of human trafficking, including ignorance, low levels of education, and a lack of formal education. He noted that an irrelevant school curriculum can lead to disinterest in education, resulting in high dropout rates. While poverty is often seen as the primary driver of trafficking, Ojomo argued that intellectual poverty, manifested through ignorance and education-related factors, plays a more significant role than material poverty. He also emphasised the impact of large family sizes, often resulting from ignorance and certain religious or traditional practices, such as polygamy, where women are turned into "baby factories." In rural areas and among illiterate, impoverished families, the inability to support a large number of children often leads to practices like traditional child placement and debt bondage. He also noted the lack of political will to

initiate or sustain anti-trafficking efforts, the absence of an effective legal framework or the failure to enforce existing laws, and the lack of funding for law enforcement agencies tasked with combating trafficking.

From the foregoing, it is clear that the factors contributing to human trafficking in South-West Nigeria are multifaceted, and these issues are exacerbated by corruption and conflict. This, in turn, creates a vulnerable population, particularly among youths, making them susceptible to exploitation and trafficking.

Demographic Pattern of human trafficking

The demographic characteristics of individuals involved in human trafficking have garnered significant attention from academic scholars who have delved into the dynamism of this phenomenon over the years. While numerous studies have shed light on certain trends and patterns, a definitive consensus on the specific demographic profile of victims and perpetrators continues to elude scholars. One prevailing school of thought asserts that human trafficking disproportionately impacts marginalised and vulnerable groups within society, a notion that finds support in a plethora of research highlighting the overrepresentation of women, children, and individuals from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds or minority communities among trafficking victims. For instance, Kevin (2001) emphasises that poverty and desperation are key factors in driving individuals into the clutches of traffickers. Similarly, Joseph's (2015) study stated that deep-rooted cultural norms and gender disparities exacerbate the heightened vulnerability of women and girls.

Moreover, research has shown that certain pattern emerges from certain geographical regions are more susceptible to the increase in human trafficking compared to others. Developing nations characterised by weak governance structures, economic volatility, and social vices often emerge as focal points for such criminal activities. For instance, Inder in 2016 emphasised the detrimental impact of corruption in enabling human trafficking to flourish unchecked in many developing countries. Similarly, the International Labour Organization (ILO) further argued that the rise in the number of male victims in various sectors such as forced labour and sexual exploitation, challenges conventional narratives and underscores the multifaceted nature of this global issue that transcends traditional gender boundaries.

It is pertinent to note that demographic patterns of human trafficking are multifaceted. Although women, children, and individuals from marginalised communities are disproportionately impacted; however, human trafficking extends beyond these groups due to a combination of factors such as socioeconomic status, geographic location, gender, and cultural norms that influence the demographic characteristics of both victims and perpetrators.

The incidence of human trafficking in Nigeria

Nigerian women and girls who fall victim to trafficking are primarily exploited for domestic servitude and sex trafficking, while boys are typically coerced into labour on plantations, commercial farms, construction sites, quarries, and mines, or are involved in petty crimes and the drug trade (Ibrahim & Omoregbe, 2020). A notable feature of the Nigerian trafficking system is the traffickers' use of charms or threats of voodoo curses to exert control over victims and coerce them into prostitution (Siddhert, 2015). For instance, once the arrangements for victims' trips are finalised, traffickers solidify the deal by bringing the victims to voodoo shrines for oath-taking ceremonies. During these rituals, body parts such as fingernails, blood, or pubic hair are collected, and the victim is made to swear an oath to repay the debt, not to report the situation to authorities, and to keep the traffickers' identities secret. The fear of breaking this covenant is so intense that it exerts a strong psychological hold over the victims, preventing them from seeking help.

Furthermore, for the past two decades, the internal trafficking of Nigerian women and children within the country has increased (UNESCO, 2006). A growing number of individuals are being trafficked from rural areas to cities like Lagos, Abeokuta, Abuja, Ibadan, Kano, Kaduna, Calabar, and Port Harcourt. This trafficking is primarily for exploitative domestic work, farm labour, prostitution, or ritual purposes (International Movement Against All Forms of Discrimination Racism, 2015; United Nations, 2017).

The Nigerian government policy and human trafficking in Nigeria

Nigeria is a signatory to the Protocol to Prevent, Suppress, and Punish Trafficking in Persons, especially Women and Children, which supplements the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime. The country has also committed to various

international human rights agreements, such as the United Nations Slavery Convention (1927), the Convention for the Suppression of Trafficking in Persons and the Exploitation of the Prostitution of Others (1949), the ILO Forced Labour Convention (1930, No. 29), the ILO Abolition of Forced Labour Convention (1957, No. 105), and the ILO Worst Forms of Child Labour Convention (1999, No. 182). Nigeria has further ratified several international treaties that extend protections to the human rights of trafficking victims, including the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (1979), the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution, and Child Pornography (2000), and the Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families (1990), among others (United States Department of State, 2015).

Within Nigeria, Section 34 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) guarantees the right to human dignity and explicitly prohibits slavery and servitude. However, while Nigeria's criminal law, governed by the Criminal Code in the Southern States and the Penal Code in the Northern States, addresses offenses related to prostitution and slavery, it lacks specific provisions directly addressing the various forms of human trafficking. This legislative gap led the Federal Government to enact the Trafficking in Persons (Prohibition), Law Enforcement, and Administration Act of 2003, which resulted in the establishment of the National Agency for the Prohibition of Traffic in Persons and Other Related Matters (NAPTIP) (Ibrahim & Omoregbe, 2020).

NAPTIP was established in 2003 to combat human trafficking through specialised units focused on investigation, counseling and rehabilitation, public enlightenment, and legal prosecution. The agency implements a strategy known as the "4Ps," which includes: (1) Prevention – raising awareness through conferences, workshops, and mass media campaigns; (2) Protection – rehabilitating and reintegrating victims into society via a National Referral Mechanism for Protection and Assistance developed in 2013; (3) Prosecution – investigating human trafficking cases, monitoring cross-border movements, and prosecuting offenders in court; and (4) Partnership – collaborating with regional and international agencies to eliminate and prevent the root causes of human trafficking in Nigeria and neighboring countries (NAPTIP, 2018).

In conclusion, Nigeria has made significant strides in combating human trafficking through international commitments and domestic laws signifies a robust framework for combating human trafficking. However, the effectiveness of these measures depends on the successful implementation and enforcement of legal provisions, alongside strong international and local partnerships to address the root causes of trafficking.

Theoretical Framework

The Routine Activity Theory

Routine Activity Theory is a sociological framework developed by Lawrence Cohen and Marcus Felson in the 1970s that focuses on the situational conditions that enable crime. The theory suggests that crime occurs when three elements converge: a motivated offender, a suitable target, and the absence of a capable guardian (Schaefer, 2021). This convergence implies that crime takes place when motivated offenders and attractive targets meet in space and time without effective guardianship. The theory's major assumptions are the presence of a constant supply of motivated offenders driven by various factors such as economic need or personal gratification, the identification of suitable targets that are valuable, vulnerable, or accessible, and the absence of capable guardians who could prevent crime through deterrence or protection (Andresen & Ha, 2017).

Despite its influence, Routine Activity Theory has faced criticisms, particularly regarding its overemphasis on opportunity while neglecting individual characteristics, social inequality, and cultural factors. Critics also question the assumption of a constant supply of motivated offenders and argue that it overlooks structural factors such as poverty and unemployment (Engström, 2020). Nonetheless, RAT remains a significant framework in criminology, particularly for its role in developing crime prevention strategies that focus on reducing opportunities for crime rather than targeting individuals.

In the context of this study, the theory provides a valuable lens for examining the persistence of human trafficking in South-west Nigeria, a region plagued by this heinous crime. The core of the theory posits that crime occurs when three elements converge: a motivated offender, a suitable target, and the absence of a capable guardian. This theoretical

framework offers insights into the complex interplay of factors contributing to the ongoing prevalence of human trafficking in the region.

Motivated offenders in human trafficking often arise from a combination of economic desperation, social marginalisation, and limited opportunities. South-west Nigeria, like other parts of the country, is characterised by high unemployment rates and lack of access to education and healthcare, creating fertile ground for individuals to be lured into the criminal underworld. The promise of a better life, often coupled with false promises of employment or education, serves as a powerful motivator for vulnerable individuals to become victims of human trafficking.

Suitable targets in human trafficking are typically individuals who are vulnerable due to their socioeconomic circumstances, lack of knowledge, or social isolation. Women and children, in particular, are often targeted due to their perceived vulnerability. Additionally, the lack of awareness and understanding of human trafficking among the general population contributes to the suitability of targets. Finally, the absence of capable guardians is a critical factor in the persistence of human trafficking in South-west Nigeria. Weak law enforcement, corruption, and ineffective governance create a permissive environment for traffickers to operate. Furthermore, the lack of shelters and support services for victims of human trafficking limits their ability to escape and seek assistance. In summary, Routine Activity Theory provides a deeper understanding of the factors contributing to the persistence of human trafficking in South-west Nigeria. The theory's emphasis on the convergence of motivated offenders, suitable targets, and the absence of capable guardians offers a comprehensive framework for addressing this ongoing phenomenon.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research approach, which is particularly appropriate given the complex and sensitive nature of human trafficking in south-west Nigeria. Qualitative approaches are suitable for researching the complex and multidimensional dynamics of human trafficking because they enable a full examination of the experiences, perceptions, and social conditions of those involved. Unlike quantitative

approaches, which may oversimplify or overlook essential aspects of the phenomenon, qualitative research enables a more in-depth understanding of the underlying elements that contribute to the persistence of human trafficking. This study aims to uncover the fundamental links between poor governance, socioeconomic factors, and regional trafficking demographic patterns by focussing on the perspectives of those directly impacted or implicated in trafficking.

We strategically chose Ogun and Lagos states as research locations due to their socioeconomic significance and proximity to international borders. Lagos State, Nigeria's largest city and commercial powerhouse, is a critical link in the trafficking network, functioning as both a source and a transit point for trafficked individuals. The state's substantial infrastructure, which includes ports and airports, makes it an important transit point for traffickers transferring victims in and out of the country. Furthermore, the high levels of economic activity in Lagos attract a large number of migrants looking for better possibilities, many of whom are prone to exploitation due to poverty, unemployment, and a lack of social support systems.

Ogun State, which borders Lagos to the north, faces similar risks due to its geographical location and socioeconomic factors. Its proximity to Benin Republic, a well-known transit route for trafficked individuals, makes it an important region of focus for this investigation. Ogun State also features a mix of urban and rural locations, which allows for an investigation into how diverse socioeconomic settings contribute to the trafficking problem. The inclusion of these two states provides a comprehensive picture of the human trafficking scene in South-west Nigeria, including both the urban dynamics of Lagos and the cross-border ramifications seen in Ogun State.

The study used snowball sampling as the primary method to choose 20 participants. Because human trafficking is a hidden and frequently stigmatised issue, snowball sampling is particularly relevant for this study. Victims, traffickers, and other important informants participating in trafficking operations are usually difficult to identify and reach using traditional sampling methods. Snowball sampling enables the researcher to contact this difficult-to-reach community by relying on referrals from first participants who are aware and have firsthand experience with trafficking. This approach produces a diverse and information-rich

sample of 5 victims, 10 former traffickers, and 5 law enforcement authorities.

Data was obtained through semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions, which are ideal for delving into the research topic's complexities and sensitivity. Semi-structured interviews provide freedom in questions, allowing the researcher to delve deeper into issues as they occur throughout the conversation. This technique is critical for capturing participants' lived experiences and nuanced viewpoints, resulting in rich, detailed data that represents the complexities of human trafficking in the region. On the other side, we conducted focus group discussions to acquire collective insights from group security officers who play comparable responsibilities in combatting trafficking networks. These debates enable us to discover common themes and patterns of inadequate governance, as well as the social dynamics that affect trafficking operations.

We used thematic analysis, a qualitative research method that involves finding, analysing, and reporting data patterns and themes, to analyse the acquired data. Thematic analysis enables the methodical organisation and interpretation of complicated qualitative data, allowing researchers to understand the fundamental causes of human trafficking in South-west Nigeria. We divided the method into several steps, starting with familiarising the data through repeated reading and preliminary coding. The researcher generated the codes directly from the data through inductive coding. This approach assures that the analysis is based on the participants' own experiences and viewpoints.

We examined and modified the categories after the initial classification to create broader themes that capture the fundamental issues related to inadequate governance, socioeconomic factors, and trafficking demographics. We examined these themes in relation to the research objectives, gaining a thorough understanding of how weak governance perpetuates human trafficking in the selected location. The approach also investigates the intersections of several themes, such as how socioeconomic variables interact with governance difficulties to increase the vulnerability of specific demographic groups to trafficking.

The investigation specifically focused on the trafficking context, encompassing the socioeconomic and cultural factors that influence victims' experiences. Thematic analysis is especially valuable in this

study because it allows for a flexible yet rigorous method of analysing qualitative data, resulting in culturally grounded and theoretically informed findings.

Theme 1: Demographic Characteristics of Victims

The demographic characteristics of victims are the specific attributes such as age, gender, location and socio-economic background that define the population targeted by traffickers or exploiters, helping to understand the patterns of the act. Therefore, the demographic characteristics of victims in south-west Nigeria are discussed in sub-themes in this chapter using the information provided by victims.

Inter-Border

Trafficking people from to south-west Nigeria often involves complex networks that operate across borders. Victims, primarily women and girls, are lured from neighboring countries like Benin, Republic of Congo and Togo among others through promises of better opportunities, education, or employment. They are often transported through informal routes, such as road and are subjected to various forms of abuse during the journey. Upon arrival in Nigeria, they are frequently trapped in forced labor, domestic servitude, or sexual exploitation. Women are often forced into prostitution, while minors are exploited for labor and domestic help. The traffickers exploit the victims' vulnerability and helplessness to control their movements and coerce them into labor or exploitation. These networks often involve different organisations that specialised mainly in human trafficking as a means of livelihood.

“We move people from different Africa countries to Nigeria. Some of my last trip were from Uganda, Togo, and Cameroon countries and from Nigeria to other parts of the world”. (female, 35 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos).

Moving people from or to any part of the world is not hard especially within African countries. Everybody is seeking for greener pasture, all we do promise them and they will follow. (male, 47 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos).

This information reveals that human trafficking networks in Africa, notably in Nigeria, operate with relative ease due to the popular desire for better chances or “greener pastures.” Traffickers take advantage of this desperation by offering false promises to potential victims, allowing

people to roam freely throughout Africa and around the world. This demonstrates how economic challenges and limited options fuel trafficking, allowing offenders to entice and influence vulnerable people with little opposition. In line with this, the study by Abiodun, Akinlade, and Oladejo (2021) found that economic challenges and bad governance fuel the persistence of human trafficking in Nigeria. The study identifies poverty, unemployment, corruption, and inadequate legislation as factors driving human trafficking, which create an environment where trafficking can thrive.

Inter-state

Inter-state trafficking in south-west Nigeria involves the movement of individuals, especially children, from northern states to urban centers like Lagos and Ibadan. These children are trafficked from Northern states, such as Kano, Kaduna and Katsina, to work as laborers and domestic help often used for labor in markets or as domestic help. Parents, often aware of the situation, are lured by promises of monetary benefits and better living conditions. However, these children are subjected to exploitation, abuse, and forced labor. The lack of effective laws and enforcement in Nigeria exacerbates the issue. Enhanced education for parents and stricter enforcement of anti-trafficking laws are crucial to addressing this problem.

While explaining the pattern and demographic characteristics of inter-state trafficking in Nigeria perpetrators asserted that, parents particularly the fathers in most cases always reach out to them willingly and unlike victims trafficked from other countries, these set of people only engage in daily job. They go out to work in the morning and come back to sleep at the accommodation provided for them by the traffickers.

“Although they are not that marketable, getting people from the north is the easiest, as some of the parents reach out willingly. While in other cases, all we need to tell the parent especially the father is that we are taking them to work and their salary will be sent to them not to their children. However, in some cases, the mother does not wish to agree to this setting but once the husband threaten her with divorce, she has no other choice than to comply” (female, 39 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos).

“I used to transport people between states in Nigeria by locating vulnerable persons in rural areas, primarily those experiencing

poverty or suffering. I'd guarantee them employment or improved living conditions in cities. I relied on local contacts, paid bribes at checkpoints, and transported them over unmonitored routes to avoid suspicion. These approaches enabled me to evade discovery and keep the operation running smoothly across the state” (female, 41 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos)

“I use my connections to relocate people from northern Nigeria to other areas. We targeted vulnerable groups with promising career prospects or education in Lagos and Ibadan. We planned transportation with the assistance of local contacts, frequently adopting informal routes to escape detection by authorities, taking advantage of lax border controls and limited surveillance” (female, 36 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos)

The findings reveal that organised networks, particularly in the northern regions, enhance inter-state trafficking in Nigeria by exploiting people's socioeconomic weaknesses. Traffickers, such as the convict in question, exploit promises of work, education, or better living conditions to attract people, particularly women and children, to move from rural areas to cities like Lagos. This is in line with the findings of Campana (2016), who asserted that human trafficking is an organised crime, as perpetrators work with their networks to carry out the deadly act.

Gender

Gender variation is significant, with women and girls constituting the majority of victims, often lured into domestic servitude, forced labor, or sexual exploitation. However, boys were also noted to among this vulnerable population, particularly to cheap labor in construction, mining and sales shops. These demographic characteristics highlight the vulnerability of certain groups to human trafficking in south-west Nigeria, emphasising the need for targeted interventions and comprehensive measures to combat this heinous crime.

The interviewed perpetrators explained that the gender identification of the victims is mostly female. Given the vulnerability of this group and societal distribution of values and role in Africa, this gender are more exposed to this unfavourable situation.

“Most of the people me and other people I know have successfully trafficked are female no boys at all. Although I know some people who do move boys to the country but it is very scarce because those parents

too always need their male children for sustenance of labour work in the farm and the likes” (female, 35 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos).

Females are more marketable than males, so my main target is always the female. (female, 35 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos).

The results demonstrate that human trafficking in Nigeria is gendered, with traffickers targeting females more frequently than males. Traffickers, like convicted criminals, prefer to traffic women and girls because of their perceived “marketability” and ease of exploitation in a range of industries, including domestic work, forced labour, and sexual exploitation. Cultural and economic factors contribute to the scarcity of trafficked men; in many rural communities, families exploit male youths for farm work or other labor-intensive chores that are necessary for family survival. This study demonstrates how socioeconomic status and gender roles influence trafficking patterns, making females more vulnerable. This study backs up Greenbaum’s 2017 claim that trafficking affects a wide range of people, particularly vulnerable populations, including women, children, and disadvantaged groups, causing severe physical and psychological distress.

Age

Certain age groups were identified to be at risk of been trafficked, this age group attract or are been targeted by perpetrators. It was noted that adolescents fall victims of inter-state and inter-border trafficking to south-west Nigeria while young adults are been targeted for trafficking from Nigeria to Western or Arab countries.

“We look for female who are desperate to leave the country by spreading the information in some circles. They will be told to pat certain amount of money for visa processing to any European countries promising them jobs. Unlike before, we don’t make it too juicy to avoid suspicions and once they do, it until they reach the destination before they will know what awaits them. For those trafficked to the country, they are usually underage” (female, 35 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos).

It was also noted by the law enforcement agents that, under age females are been trafficked to the region while adult females are been trafficked outside the country.

“From our observation, we have noticed that majority of the victims that we rescued that are been trafficked outside Nigeria are adult female while does that were trafficked to the country were female adolescents” (male, 37 years old, NAPTIP officer, Lagos).

The findings demonstrate significant age-based patterns in human trafficking across borders and within Nigerian regions. Traffickers primarily traffic adult females outside the country, while they traffic children under the age of 18 into the region from elsewhere. Divergent demands in the trafficking market reflect this distinction: traffickers frequently traffic adult women overseas under false pretences for forced labour or sexual exploitation, while they typically smuggle minors into the country for domestic servitude and other forms of exploitation. This supports the findings of Patterson and Zhuo (2017), who concluded in their study that mostly adolescent and adult females are used for forced labour and sex workers.

“People are already waiting before the goods arrive but most of them are owners of local restaurants (buka) who always in need of helpers as kitchen assistant and waiter, store owners and oga’s madams (rich men’s wives)” (female, 29 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos).

This group of people narrated that; they orientate these victims before they are been given out to their respective employer. According to them, the victims are be coerced using their family and other personal information so that they won’t misbehave when they are with their employers. They highlighted that this is a way to motivate them to perform effective in their place of employment.

“First thing I do before potential employer arrives is to give them a sound warning on how they should behave handing them over. Once I tell them that those money, I promised to be sending to the parents monthly will be from their monthly steepens, they will have no choice than to behave” (female, 42 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos)

The victims, according to the perpetrators are always been grouped based on their assessment of their potentials. Most of the time the victims does not know the kind of job they are coming to do in Nigeria and according to them, the parents does not worry about it as far as it can be sorting for their immediate needs. It was discovered that parents of the victims are of the view that no matter what the children will be doing at the host country, it better than them getting useless at home doing

nothing and it will reduce the number of mouths they feed at home while providing additional sources of income for them.

“To better utilise them, I would have assessed them by engaging them in a deep conversation. That way I would have known their personality and what they have zeal for. After the assessment, I grade them into 3 categories according to their performance. The third category is the lowest so I know I will present them to people running local restaurants and they will fetch me just little money. The second category are fair, they most time just required little bit of grooming and all so I present these set to my rich clients who as warehouses and stores for their business they most consist people who sell goods like fabric, kitchen utensils and home appliances among others at large scale. While my first grade are always little but they fetch me money the most, what I make on them is more than the profits of the second and third together. I spend a lot of efforts on these set because I always present them as escort” (male, 57 years old, convicted perpetrator, Lagos)

The information provided above indicates that inter-border and inter-state trafficking is a prevalent activity in south-west Nigeria. The findings reveal that these victims serve a variety of purposes, from domestic servants to prostitution, and that their parents or legal guidance consent to their movement from their home to this region, with the majority being female. Similarly, in South-west Nigeria, particularly in states like Lagos, the information shows that inter-state trafficking is a pervasive issue. Northern states like Kano and Katsina traffic children to work as labourers and domestic help. Promises of monetary benefits and better living conditions often lure parents, who are aware of the situation. However, these children are subjected to exploitation, abuse, and forced labor. The promise of a better future lures young female adults to other parts of the world, only to expose them to exploitation. In line with these findings, the study of Bako and Syed (2018) concluded that aside from poverty, additional factors that contribute to these issues are gender inequality, limited educational opportunities, and societal and cultural traditions that sustain the exploitation of specific groups. Furthermore, these findings corroborate the findings of Kiss et al. (2022), emphasising that trafficked women and girls endure diverse forms of physical, sexual, and psychological abuse, often intensified by poverty, inadequate education, and restricted social support.

Theme 2: Drivers of Human Trafficking

Human trafficking in South-west Nigeria is a complex and deeply rooted issue, fueled by various socio-economic challenges that plague the region. Poverty stands as a significant driver, forcing vulnerable populations into situations where they become easy targets for traffickers. Many individuals, desperate to escape the grip of poverty, are lured by promises of better opportunities, only to find themselves trapped in exploitative conditions. Food insecurity further exacerbates this situation, as the struggle to access basic necessities pushes individuals into desperate measures, often leading them into the hands of traffickers. The constant battle for survival leaves little room for consideration of the risks involved. Additionally, the broader context of insecurity creates an environment where trafficking networks can thrive. The lack of adequate protection and enforcement mechanisms allows these networks to operate with impunity, perpetuating the cycle of exploitation. This confluence of poverty, food insecurity, and general insecurity creates a fertile ground for human trafficking, leaving countless individuals at risk.

Poverty

Poverty is a fundamental cause of human trafficking in South-west Nigeria, creating a fertile environment for exploitation and abuse. In Africa, where economic opportunities are limited and social safety nets are weak, many individuals find themselves trapped in a cycle of poverty that leaves them vulnerable to traffickers. The desperation that stems from chronic poverty forces people, especially women, to seek out any means of survival, often making them easy targets for those who prey on their vulnerability. The lack of access to education, employment, and basic social services further exacerbates this issue, pushing individuals to accept risky offers that promise a better life but lead to exploitation. Traffickers exploit these dire economic conditions, offering deceptive promises of employment, education, or a better future abroad, which all too often result in forced labour, sexual exploitation, or other forms of modern slavery. In essence, poverty not only creates the conditions that make trafficking possible but also sustains the networks that perpetuate this human rights violation.

“I was born into a small village with little or no knowledge of education or the amenities of the modern world, our village was

plagued by hunger, thirst and despair. I remember days when we had to go without food, and nights when my siblings would cry themselves to sleep on empty stomach. My parent worked tirelessly but their labour never sufficed to provide us with basic needs” (female, age 27 years old, victim Lagos).

“I found female adults to be extremely easy targets, especially those that have the sense of responsibility towards their families, All I had to do was promise them a golden opportunity of breakthrough where their family lives and situation would change forever based on the decision they make at the very moment, and backing my claims up with little incentives” (male, 36 years old Perpetrator Lagos).

Based on this information, it is evident that poverty, which stems from a complex interplay of factors, is one of the major drivers of human trafficking in this region, which perpetrators leverage. The lack of education and other necessary social amenities in the rural areas of African countries, including Nigeria, exacerbates the vulnerability of individuals to human trafficking. Traffickers can exploit these factors by luring individuals with promises of better opportunities or forcing them into desperate situations. In Nigeria, poor governance significantly contributes to the occurrence of human trafficking activities. This is in line with the findings of Ariadne, Pratamawaty, and Limilia (2021), who asserted that the continuous human trafficking in Indonesia erupts from poverty and corruption.

Ineffective leadership has resulted in limited access to essential services like education and healthcare, perpetuating cycles of poverty. In addition, corruption and lack of transparency of governments have led to misallocation of resources, hindering development and the escalation of poverty, inequality, and limited opportunities in many African countries. Without access to education, individuals are unable to acquire the skills needed for gainful employment, perpetuating a cycle of poverty. The absence of essential social amenities like healthcare and infrastructure further marginalises rural communities, limiting their potential for development and contributing to the widening gap between urban and rural areas. This is in support of the finding of who narrated that by exploiting the despair of individuals, traffickers deceitfully lure them with deceptive assurances of job opportunities, education, or an improved life overseas, only to subsequently subject them to involuntary

servitude, sexual exploitation, or various other sorts of mistreatment (Wuyah and Mailamba 2019).

Food insecurity

Food insecurity plays a critical role in driving human trafficking in Africa, where the lack of consistent access to sufficient and nutritious food forces many individuals into precarious situations. In this region, the struggle to meet basic nutritional needs often leads to desperation, pushing people to seek any means necessary to secure food for themselves and their families. This desperate quest for survival makes them highly vulnerable to traffickers who exploit their need for sustenance. Traffickers prey on the vulnerable by offering deceptive promises of work, food, or financial stability, which ultimately lead to exploitation and abuse. The pervasive hunger and malnutrition experienced by many in this region weaken social and familial bonds, leaving individuals isolated and more susceptible to the lure of traffickers. As food insecurity continues to ravage communities, it not only exacerbates poverty but also entrenches the conditions that allow human trafficking to flourish. This vicious cycle underscores the profound impact of food insecurity on the lives of those who are most at risk, perpetuating a cycle of exploitation that is difficult to escape.

“I have lived my entire life with a scheduling duration of which meals to eat and thinking of what to eat the following day, living one day at a time, I have never had choices about my own sustenance, let alone aspects of life. I have never known the comfort of a full fridge or the joy of having to sit down and have a favorite meal which I don’t even have at the moment” (female, age 28 years old, victim Lagos)

“We have struggled with coping on daily meals as most of my family members are deeply affected by malnutrition, going to school wasn’t an option when we couldn’t afford to put proper meals on the table, our community has been deeply affected by contaminated water proving fatal to our health” (female, 26 years old, victim Lagos)

The victims of human trafficking suffer from food insecurity, which is an end result of poverty. Food insecurity contributes to poverty by limiting individuals’ productivity and earning potential. This makes it even harder for people to escape poverty and meet their basic needs. Corruption, which stems from poor governance, has a significant impact on food security through resource mismanagement. This ineffective

leadership style has resulted in inefficient agricultural production, limited food access, and food price inflation. When people are unable to meet their basic needs, they become more vulnerable to exploitation through desperation, which will lead individuals to accept dangerous or exploitative situations in search of food or income. Traffickers then exploit their need for sustenance in order to control and manipulate them. This, in turn, led to forced labor, sexual exploitation, and other forms of human trafficking. According to Oyindamola, Bidemi, and Atta's 2023 study, traffickers exploit the despair of individuals by deceiving them with false promises of employment opportunities, education, or a better life overseas, only to subject them to involuntary labor, sexual abuse, or other forms of mistreatment.

Insecurity

Insecurity is a powerful force driving human trafficking in Africa, where the intertwining challenges of poverty and food insecurity exacerbate the vulnerability of individuals and communities. The pervasive threat of violence, instability, and lack of law enforcement creates an environment where traffickers can operate with impunity, exploiting those already weakened by poverty and hunger. In the northern regions and other parts of African countries where insecurity reigns, people are often displaced, stripped of their livelihoods, and left without access to basic needs such as food and shelter. This deepens their desperation, pushing them into the hands of traffickers who offer deceptive promises of safety, employment, and sustenance. The lack of a secure environment not only fuels the conditions that make trafficking possible but also perpetuates a cycle of exploitation and abuse. As insecurity spreads, it tears apart the social fabric, eroding trust and making it nearly impossible for communities to protect their most vulnerable members. Thus, insecurity acts as a catalyst, amplifying the impact of poverty and food insecurity, and driving the human trafficking crisis that continues to plague South-west Nigeria.

"I don't have a decent job at home, so when she promised that I can get a good paying job that does not require certificate I was tempted. Then I thought it worth given a try since I never know how God can intervene in my life. Given my family condition, i don't mind taking any chance, no matter how little it could be" (female, age 28 years old, victim Lagos)

“The northern parts of the country that we have noticed to be targeted by human traffickers are always the place that violence are occurring. They already know this people are desperate and as such they leverage on that to take advantage of people particular females” (male, 42 years old, NAPTIP officer, Lagos).

We have identified some of these people rescued from traffickers to be from African countries that are experiencing insecurity due to constant violence, economic hardship or war breakout. I believe those traffickers are definitely leveraging on the desperations of these people (male, 32 years old, NAPTIP officer, Lagos).

“Human trafficking remains a significant concern in Nigeria, with perpetrators exploiting vulnerable individuals amidst the prevailing insecurity. Our department has identified a correlation between human trafficking and other security threats including violent, kidnapping and low food supply” (male, 37 years old, NAPTIP officer, Lagos).

This information shows that insecurity, whether it manifests as conflict, political instability, or economic hardship, creates fertile ground for human trafficking to flourish. Violence and economic hardships beset societies, making individuals more vulnerable to exploitation. Traffickers use these conditions to deceive, coerce, and force people into servitude. Conflict zones, in particular, offer traffickers opportunities to operate with impunity. The breakdown of law and order, coupled with the displacement of populations, creates a power vacuum that traffickers can exploit. Vulnerable individuals, often fleeing violence and seeking safety, are more susceptible to false promises and coercion.

Additionally, the chaos and instability of conflict can hinder effective law enforcement, making it difficult to suspect trafficking and protect victims. Moreover, economic insecurity can also drive individuals into the hands of traffickers. When faced with poverty, unemployment, and limited opportunities, people may be more willing to take risks or accept exploitative offers in the hope of a better life. Traffickers prey on these vulnerabilities, promising lucrative jobs or opportunities abroad that often turn out to be deceptive. Economic hardship can create desperation, making individuals more susceptible to manipulation and coercion. In line with this, Rana’s study (2024) also asserted that places with limited economic opportunities and conflict zones created an avenue for traffickers to operate with impunity.

Theme 3: Weak Institution

Weak institutions play a pivotal role in fostering an environment conducive to human trafficking. When governments lack the capacity or will to enforce laws, protect human rights, and provide essential services, individuals become more vulnerable to exploitation. Corruption within government agencies has created opportunities for traffickers to operate with impunity. Bribery and collusion between officials and traffickers has hindered investigations, delay prosecutions, and undermine the effectiveness of anti-trafficking efforts. Lack of law enforcement capacity has also facilitate human trafficking. Underfunded, poorly trained, or corrupt police forces will be unable to effectively investigate and apprehend traffickers. This can deter victims from reporting crimes and embolden perpetrators.

Corruption within the security system

Institutional flaws that induce corruption in the security system directly contribute to trafficking by enabling traffickers to operate freely. Bribery and coordination between security personnel and traffickers provide a protective barrier, allowing traffickers to bypass checkpoints, avoid punishment, and obtain the release of arrested members. This corrupt milieu discourages effective law enforcement, as officers prioritise personal gain over justice, undermining anti-trafficking efforts. As a result, traffickers feel empowered since they can manipulate or buy their way out of legal difficulties. This cycle fosters trafficking, making it more difficult to disrupt networks and safeguard victims.

“As a border personnel, I can confirm that corruption is a major issue. Some officers accept money from traffickers, allowing them to cross without examination. This guarantees compensation, enabling traffickers to continue their operations. Because of a lack of accountability in the system, corruption frequently goes undetected, thereby contributing to the perpetuation of people trafficking along the border” (male, 47 years old, officer, Ogun State).

“Corruption has hampered efforts to curb human trafficking in Nigeria. Many traffickers evade justice by bribing police officials or using political ties, making arrests and prosecutions difficult. This impunity provides a safe environment for traffickers, allowing them to continue exploiting vulnerable individuals. Without addressing corruption within our institutions, it is extremely difficult to stop the

cycle of trafficking and protect individuals in danger” (male, 37 years old, NAPTIB officer, Ogun State).

“By hindering law enforcement operations, corruption has allowed human trafficking to continue in Nigeria. Traffickers frequently bribe officials to ignore unlawful operations or release arrested suspects, undermining investigations and convictions. This creates a cycle in which traffickers operate with impunity, knowing they can profit from unethical activities. As a result, victims’ trust in the police erodes, and they are less likely to disclose crimes, which perpetuates the trafficking network” (male, 37 years old, Police officer, Ogun State).

It is evidence from this findings corruption has significantly contributed to the survival of human trafficking activities in South-west Nigeria by compromising the effectiveness of law enforcement and justice systems. With traffickers bribing security agents, it impede investigations and typically release arrested individuals without charges. By enabling traffickers to operate without fear of prosecution, this undermines the rule of law. Corrupt behaviour in law enforcement and other institutions undermines institutional integrity, lowering public trust and discouraging victims from reporting crimes. As a result, trafficking continues unabated, continuing the cycle of exploitation and diminishing the government’s ability to safeguard its citizens.

Inadequate financial resources

Inadequate financial resources for security officers, which result from poor governance, play a crucial role in the persistence of human trafficking in Nigeria. Insufficient budget results in poorly equipped and underpaid officers, limiting their ability to adequately investigate and prosecute traffickers. This shortage of resources frequently leads to compromised integrity, as some officials resort to accepting bribes to augment their income. Furthermore, poor training and equipment diminish security personnel’ ability to respond to trafficking situations, allowing traffickers to operate with little resistance. As a result, human trafficking networks thrive in a climate characterised by lax enforcement and accountability.

“Underfunding leaves us with insufficient resources and low salaries, reducing morale and effectiveness. We lack the necessary equipment, trucks, and communication capabilities to locate and apprehend traffickers. This makes it easier for traffickers to exploit vulnerabilities in our operations. Limited financial assistance also means that fewer

workers are available for preventive measures, allowing human trafficking networks to thrive in the absence of effective deterrence” (male, 37 years old, Police officer, Ogun State).

“Inadequate resources limits our capacity to conduct extensive investigations and public awareness initiatives. We frequently lack the resources required for monitoring, victim rescue, and rehabilitation assistance. Furthermore, low financial support impacts our training programs, diminishing our ability to successfully battle traffickers. This financial constraint suggests that traffickers encounter less resistance and can persist in their activities, aware that insufficient funds hinder enforcement efforts” (male, 37 years old, NAPTIB officer, Ogun State)

“Because of limited budget, we are facing shortages of vital equipment such as scanners, police vehicles, and surveillance systems. This complicates monitoring and policing trafficking networks, especially at remote border crossings. A shortage of financial resources also means fewer personnel, resulting in gaps in coverage and more opportunities for traffickers to transport people unnoticed. Underfunding impairs our ability to police border security, allowing trafficking networks to operate more freely” (male, 47 years old, officer, Ogun State).

The study shows that inadequate budget allocation limits security officials’ operating capabilities and resources, impeding their ability to combat human trafficking effectively. This lack of funding has an impact on critical areas like training, equipment, and monitoring, jeopardising their ability to detect and disrupt trafficking networks. Lack of finances leads to less research, poor border monitoring, and less effective victim protection. As a result, traffickers exploit these flaws, working with a lower risk of detection and prosecution, allowing human trafficking operations to continue and expand. Chikaodili, 2021 research revealed that Nigerian law enforcement authorities sometimes engage in trafficking network collusion due to lack of financial resources, and poor training.

Weak legislation

In Nigeria, inadequate enforcement contributes considerably to the prevalence of human trafficking. Inadequate legislation and loopholes enable traffickers to operate with little fear of prosecution. Victims’ limited legal protections dissuade them from seeking justice, allowing traffickers to operate with relative impunity. Inadequate legislative

supervision and weak enforcement of current laws impede comprehensive anti-trafficking measures, allowing criminal networks to thrive. As a result, trafficking persists, aided by a legal system that lacks the strength and consistency to properly address it.

“Weak legislation limits our ability to combat human trafficking effectively. Many traffickers make use of legal loopholes to avoid harsh penalties, knowing that the current legal framework is insufficient. This makes it difficult to get convictions or prevent others from engaging in trafficking activities, allowing the problem to continue” (male, 37 years old, Police officer, Ogun State).

“Weak legislation hinders our work by providing minimal punishment for traffickers and inadequate protection for survivors. The absence of clear norms and comprehensive regulations makes it difficult to prosecute offenders efficiently, resulting in dismissals or mild punishments. This environment allows traffickers to continue their abuse of vulnerable communities without fear of repercussions” (male, 37 years old, NAPITB officer, Ogun State)

“Weak law has left gaps in border security for traffickers to exploit. We cannot adequately monitor and intercept traffickers due to limited resources and ambiguous instructions. Because there are no strict fines or enforcement procedures in place, traffickers feel comfortable crossing borders with victims, knowing they will face minimal legal consequences” (male, 47 years old, officer, Ogun State).

This result shows that Nigeria’s negligent administration has greatly aided the survival of human trafficking by creating an environment conducive to weak legislation, inadequate law enforcement, and corruption. Weak legislation, with loopholes and simple fines, does not deter traffickers, allowing them to target vulnerable groups with little risk. It is clear that these ineffective legislative frameworks lead to inefficient prosecutions and insufficient victim protection, allowing traffickers to flee justice. It is also obvious that poor governance leads to limited resources, limiting effective control and surveillance. Traffickers take advantage of these loopholes, moving victims across international and domestic borders with little chance of facing substantial legal penalties. Together, these traits foster an environment in which trafficking networks can thrive, knowing that governance flaws will shield them from accountability, perpetuating the cycle of exploitation. This is in line with the study of Chikaodili 2021, who asserted that the

lack of efficient law enforcement adds to the continued existence of human trafficking, as it creates the perception that these crimes would not be punished.

Conclusion

The findings of this study present a bleak picture of people trafficking in south-west Nigeria, encompassing both cross-border and interstate operations. Under false pretenses of greater opportunities, traffickers traffic victims, typically women and girls, from bordering countries and northern Nigerian states, only to exploit, force them into labor, and assault them. Traffickers take advantage of economic desperation and insufficient law enforcement by operating through informal channels and abusing socioeconomic vulnerabilities. Gender and age significantly impact trafficking patterns, disproportionately impacting women and adolescents. The research highlights the significance of targeted interventions, stricter enforcement of anti-trafficking laws, and more educational campaigns to protect vulnerable persons and disrupt trafficking networks. Addressing the root causes, such as poverty and gender inequality, is crucial in combating this prevalent issue.

The findings concluded that the key causes of human trafficking in South-west Nigeria: extreme poverty, food insecurity, and instability. Poverty creates an excellent atmosphere for exploitation, with traffickers preying on the despair of those struggling to survive. Food insecurity makes people more vulnerable, putting them into risky situations where traffickers exploit their desire for basic necessities. Insecurity exacerbates these concerns by causing destabilisation in communities, eroding social structures, and allowing traffickers to operate freely. Together, these aspects establish a cyclical pattern of exploitation in which economic hardship and instability increase people's vulnerability to trafficking. Addressing these root causes through targeted interventions, improved governance, and greater security measures is crucial for avoiding human trafficking and protecting vulnerable populations.

The study also concluded that human trafficking in south-west Nigeria persists because of weak institutions. Corruption in the security system allows traffickers to operate freely because bribery and collusion between traffickers and authorities inhibit law enforcement efforts. Inadequate financial resources exacerbate the problem by leaving

security personnel underequipped and underpaid, restricting their ability to combat trafficking. Furthermore, weak laws, such as legal gaps and insufficient victim rights, impede traffickers' prosecution. These institutional flaws foster the formation of trafficking networks, which exploit people's vulnerabilities and perpetuate a cycle of exploitation and abuse. Addressing these weaknesses through comprehensive reforms is crucial to improving the effectiveness of anti-trafficking measures and protecting vulnerable groups.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following to address human trafficking in South-west Nigeria:

1. **Strengthen Anti-Trafficking Legislation and Enforcement:** The government should amend and execute comprehensive anti-trafficking legislation to address legal loopholes and stiffen punishments for traffickers. Law enforcement authorities should receive proper training and equipment to effectively handle human trafficking cases.
2. **Combat Corruption in Law Enforcement:** The government should enforce strict anti-corruption measures within security and border control agencies, establish transparent processes for reporting and addressing corruption, and hold officials accountable for misconduct.
3. **Increase Funding and Resources for Security Agencies:** The government should provide sufficient funding to law enforcement and anti-trafficking units, as well as invest in training, equipment, and technology, to improve their ability to investigate and dismantle trafficking networks.
4. **Address Socio-Economic Drivers:** To lessen vulnerable people's susceptibility to trafficking, the government should promote and support initiatives that alleviate poverty and food insecurity while also providing education, vocational training, and economic opportunities.
5. **Enhance Public Awareness and Victim Support:** The government should launch public awareness campaigns to educate communities about the dangers of trafficking and available support services, as

well as establish comprehensive victim support systems, such as safe shelters, legal assistance, and rehabilitation programs, to assist survivors in their recovery and reintegration.

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